

DATA SCIENCE AND MATHEMATICS: THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS AND PRACTICAL APPLICATIONS

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Annotation. *This annotation scientifically analyzes the fundamental role of mathematics in the field of Data Science. Data Science is an integral part of the modern information society and makes it possible to process, analyze, and forecast large volumes of data. Data science is a synthesis of computer science, data analysis, and statistics, and its efficiency and reliability directly rely on mathematical tools. In these processes, subjects such as linear algebra, probability theory, mathematical analysis, and discrete mathematics play a significant role. In the article, the practical application of these mathematical directions in Data Science is illustrated through examples. In the article, broad attention is given to the role and importance of fundamental mathematical branches in the field of Data Science. The article proves that without mathematical knowledge it is impossible to gain deep knowledge and skills in the field of Data Science. Mathematics and its principles serve as the main technical foundation of the Data Science field and play an important role in understanding the essence of data, creating algorithms, and optimizing models.*

Key words: *data analysis, computer science, statistics, mathematical analysis, machine learning, linear regression, logic, PCA, SVM.*

Аннотация: *В данной аннотации на научной основе анализируется фундаментальная роль математики в области науки о данных. Наука о данных является неотъемлемой частью современного информационного общества, позволяя обрабатывать, анализировать и прогнозировать большие объемы данных. Наука о данных представляет собой синтез областей информатики, анализа данных и статистики, и ее эффективность и надежность напрямую зависят от математических инструментов. Эти процессы имеют большое значение в таких дисциплинах, как линейная алгебра, теория вероятностей, математический анализ и дискретная математика. В статье на примерах иллюстрируется практическое применение этих математических областей в науке о данных. В статье рассматривается роль и значение фундаментальных математических разделов в области науки о данных. Доказывается, что невозможно получить глубокие знания и навыки в области науки о данных без математических знаний. Математика и ее принципы служат основной технической опорой области науки о данных и играют важную роль в понимании сущности данных, создании алгоритмов и оптимизации моделей в них.*

Ключевые слова: *анализ данных, информатика, статистика, математический анализ, машинное обучение, линейная регрессия, логика, PCA, SVM.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu annotatsiyada Data Science sohasida matematikaning fundamental o'ri ilmiy asosda tahlil qilinadi. Data Science zamonaviy axborot jamiyatining ajralmas qismi bo'lib, katta hajmdagi ma'lumotlarni qayta ishlash, tahlil qilish va prognozlash imkonini beradi.*

Data Science kompyuter fanlari, ma'lumotlar tahlili va statistika sohalari sintezi bo'lib, uning samaradorligi va ishonchliligi bevosita matematik vositalarga tayanadi.

Mazkur jarayonlarda chiziqli algebra, ehtimollar nazariyasi, matematik tahlil va diskret matematika kabi fanlar katta ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada ushbu matematik yo'nalishlarning Data Science'dagi amaliy qo'llanilishi misollar orqali yoritilgan. Shuningdek, Data Science sohasidagi fundamental matematik tarmoqlarning o'rni va ahamiyatiga keng e'tibor qaratilgan.

Maqola matematik bilimlarsiz Data Science sohasida chuqur bilim va ko'nikmalarga ega bo'lish mumkin emasligini asoslab beradi. Matematika va uning prinsiplari Data Science sohasining asosiy texnik tayanchi bo'lib xizmat qiladi hamda ma'lumotlar mohiyatini tushunish, algoritmlar yaratish va modellarni optimallashtirishda muhim rol o'ynaydi.

Kalit so'zlar: *Ma'lumotlar tahlili, kompyuter fanlari, statistika, matematik tahlil, machine learning, chiziqli regressiya, mantiq, PCA, SVM.*

Data science plays an important role in modern decision-making, as it allows organizations to obtain practical understanding from large and complex data sets. Data science also integrates domain knowledge from its main application areas (for example, natural sciences, information technology, and medicine). Data science is multifaceted, and it can be defined as a science, research paradigm, research method, science, work process, and profession.

Data science is closely connected with mathematics. That is, the science of mathematics is considered the fundamental root of the data science field. The data science field uses various tools and methods in analyzing data and in collecting different types of data to draw conclusions, and these methods apply mathematical principles. Many branches of mathematics play an important role in data science. Including, it is closely connected with fields such as linear algebra, statistics and probability theory, mathematical analysis and optimization, and discrete mathematics.

Linear algebra. To master any field of computing or technology, it is necessary to understand linear algebra. As the study of matrices and the operations acting on them, linear algebra is the mathematical foundation of almost all algorithms and analyses used in computers. However, its presentation in textbooks over decades differs from how professionals use linear algebra to solve modern applications.

Linear algebra is the main mathematical foundation of Data Science. Data are often represented in the form of vectors and matrices. For example:

-**PCA** (Principal Component Analysis) — dimensionality reduction

-**SVD** (Singular Value Decomposition) — data compression and analysis, thereby identifying important features

-**SVM** (Support Vector Machine) — classification problems

All of these methods are based on performing operations on matrices.

In data science, when working with data, the data are mainly in tabular form, and we can imagine these data as vectors and matrices. When working with algorithms: many data learning (that is, machine learning) algorithms, linear regression (that is, linear regression).

Statistics and probability theory. This branch of mathematics provides several methods that help data analysts work with large data: Hypothesis testing: the main aspect of the analysis process tests hypotheses and evaluates mutually exclusive data.

Creating probability distributions and estimation: applying statistical methods to data helps to create probability distributions and estimation, which in turn helps to better understand logistic regression and machine learning. Creating learning algorithms: algorithms such as Bayes and logistic regression have been developed to meet the needs of data analysis. The role of probability theory in data science is mainly evident in measuring uncertainty, making predictions, and working with algorithms and similar areas.

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Optimization. Machine learning models are optimized using many gradient descent methods. The purpose of such optimization is to find a set of model parameters that minimizes a given loss function. In this field, it is impossible to proceed without mathematical analysis. It is applied in developing regression, classification, and data clustering algorithms.

Discrete mathematics. Discrete mathematics plays an important role in the field of data science, because it focuses on analyzing data not as uncertain, but as precise, separated elements. Discrete mathematics provides the main theoretical foundations for creating algorithms and analyzing them in the field of data science. Discrete mathematics is the mathematical form of programming. When we work in any programs, we first think about building the program and its algorithms, that is, we try to create its mathematical model. Whether it is in our mind or written, we perform it by dividing it into certain steps. For us, it is simply thinking and reasoning, but from a scientific point of view, all of this constitutes discrete mathematics. In discrete mathematics, understanding algorithms, graph theory, combinatorics, logic, and cryptography and others are closely related to the field of data science. That is, it can also be said as the mathematical root of data science.

Discrete mathematics forms the theoretical basis of algorithms and computational processes. It is often emphasized that to become a data science specialist one must be strong in mathematics or fully master mathematical knowledge, however, the most important thing is knowing and understanding how and where to use it correctly. We cannot directly teach others simply by strongly learning some subject. For this, we also need to learn pedagogical knowledge and improve our qualifications. Similarly, in this field as well, we can achieve results through searching and striving. Many of us associate the foundation of the Data Science field with programming and artificial intelligence, but mathematics lies at its core. The Data Science field is not only programming. It is a field that requires deep knowledge of mathematics in order to imagine the world of large-scale data and use it effectively.

In conclusion, data science (Data Science) is one of the most important directions of modern science and technology, and its effective development directly relies on mathematical knowledge. In particular, linear algebra, probability theory, mathematical analysis, and discrete mathematics form the theoretical and practical foundation of Data Science. With the help of these mathematical directions, complex data are analyzed, algorithms are created, and forecasting processes are carried out. Also, mathematical approaches play an important role in increasing the accuracy and reliability of models. Therefore, to become a mature specialist in the field of Data Science, mathematical thinking and deep theoretical knowledge are necessary.

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